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INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technology is a challenge that companies must face. Innovations and applications based on information and communication technologies (ICT) have become the main driving force for improving organizational performance, economic growth and social change. Information and communication technologies have become a valuable business tool for entrepreneurs. Information and communication technology, education/training and research and development are among the most important elements for creating an entrepreneurial platform. Entrepreneurship and ICT require skills to adapt to current economic trends. Its use is economically more expensive and promising for business. The company's IT capabilities are essential for better website

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the importance of information technology adoption for government to derive an information technology value chain that is beneficial to all aspects of efforts to improve efficiency and effectiveness. Information technology has a very important effect on the performance of employees, because it helps to perform all activities faster, accurately and correctly. In general, this study is important to understand and understand that information technology is necessary and useful for enterprises. Enterprise must have advantages, core competitiveness, strategies and innovations, especially information technology.

management, as they can depict comprehensive information and electronic payment systems.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Information technology affects various activities, especially when it comes to organizing business processes to adapt information technology to its environment. Therefore, it is necessary to discuss in depth what information technologies are used. Information technology affects internal control because it shows more acceptable results. In addition, activities including marketing, finance, resources are inseparable from the development of information technology, because it helps to implement it. Technological advancement is affecting its operations to survive from competitors.

RESULTS

Inactivity in the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) has grown rapidly in recent years. Nowadays, most modern ICT products, i.e. iPods, mobile phones, personal organizers and digital televisions, can easily be used for satellite communication technologies, personal computers and the World Wide Web. This new technology helps organizations maximize information retrieval and sharing and distribution through electronic publications. It allows people to communicate directly with others around the world from home or office. Information technology is very necessary for long and long distances as it

helps in communication and coordination to realize the company's achievements. The revolution in the field of information technology should be made in such a way that the company is ready to compete with other companies in its management.

CONCLUSION

In the application of information and communication technologies, various companies are using very complete and modern technologies. It is important to understand that information and communication technologies will not make a difference if they are not supported by sufficient human resources and work culture to operate these tools.

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